

Research and protection of Culture in Cyprus

*Challenges and pitfalls of the
Cypriot Copyright Legislation*

Philippe Jougleux

Professor, School of Law, European University Cyprus

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Research and protection of culture in Cyprus: challenges and pitfalls of the Cypriot Copyright legislation

Research study for KR21

Philippe Jougleux,

Professor, School of Law, European University Cyprus, p.jougleux@euc.ac.cy

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1. Executive Summary

This expert opinion provides a comprehensive analysis of the legal framework governing research, teaching, and library activities under Cypriot copyright law, with particular attention to the challenges arising from the current legislative landscape and its interaction with European Union (EU) law, and formulates legislative recommendations.

The Study first presents the specific challenges of Cypriot copyright law and then discusses the exceptions relevant to research and education. It follows with listing other related mechanisms of copyright and contract law and then concludes with a specific list of policy proposals, both legislative and non-legislative.

Specifically, the main findings and proposals of the study are that:

- Cypriot copyright law (Law 59/1976) combines a common law tradition with successive EU harmonisation layers, resulting in an incoherent and unnecessarily complex legislative text.
- The Copyright and Related Rights Authority is not yet operational, effectively suspending several key mechanisms: the private copy levy, public lending remuneration, and the licensing transparency required for the e-teaching carve-out.
- The collective management infrastructure remains underdeveloped, with most active CMOs being branches of Greek CMOs. No payment has yet been made under the public lending mechanism.
- The teaching and e-teaching exceptions have been rendered practically inoperative because of the establishment of a 5% usage threshold — far below the 15% allowed in Germany and the absence of any cap in most EU Member States — combined with mandatory fair compensation and a licensing carve-out.
- The quotation exception and the fair dealing exception could offer meaningful flexibility in research and education contexts if interpreted in light of CJEU case law. However, this possibility of broad interpretation is widely misunderstood in practice.
- The text and data mining exceptions are faithfully transposed from EU law and are relevant for research organisations, though their application to generative AI training remains contested.

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- The orphan works mechanism has never been used in Cyprus due to administrative complexity and lack of awareness.
 - Cyprus has no secondary publication right, no operative public lending mechanism, and no private copy levy in practice. I
 - Cyprus' 2022 National Open Science Policy targets universal open access by 2026, yet the legislative framework does not currently support this ambition.
 - There is a need to comprehensively re-codify Law 59/1976 to restore legislative coherence and eliminate contradictions accumulated through successive amendments.
 - It is of tremendous importance to make the Cypriot Copyright Authority operational without delay; its inaction currently paralyses multiple mechanisms of the copyright system.
 - A consideration should be made on whether to raise or abolish the 5% threshold in the teaching and e-teaching exceptions to align with EU law and comparative Member State practice.
 - A secondary publication right for publicly funded research should be introduced, in anticipation of forthcoming EU-level intervention through the European Research Area Act.
 - Awareness-raising initiatives for educational institutions and libraries should be launched on the actual scope of the quotation exception, the orphan works mechanism, and the out-of-commerce works regime.

2. Introduction

The study aims to propose a cartography of the legal framework of research and teaching in Cyprus with emphasis on the challenges and pitfalls of the Cypriot Copyright legislation. To do so, it is first necessary, by way of introduction, to note the specificities of the Cypriot copyright law by studying its history (2.1). This should be read, however, in conjunction with a more practical analysis of the copyright law's ecosystem in Cyprus (2.2) Subsection 2.3 will then focus specifically on the methodology adopted to analyse the legal framework governing research and education in Cypriot copyright law.

2.1. Overview of Cypriot copyright law

Cyprus copyright law originated in British colonial times and has evolved through EU harmonization. Key legislation began with Law 59/1976¹, modernized extensively for EU accession in 2004² and further aligned with the following EU acquis on Copyright law. In the field of Copyright law and following the Brexit, Cyprus remains one of the few countries in the EU with a common law tradition³. This specificity is of great importance, as International Copyright law was for a long time characterized by an ideological and legal divide between continental law countries and common law countries, although elements of convergence of civil law and common law rights systems can be perceived in the contemporary era⁴. In this regard, the ability of Cyprus to incorporate and apply EU Copyright law can be seen as a measure of the degree of harmonization of this field in EU. It should be noted that in Cypriot constitutional law, EU law is explicitly considered as the supreme source of law,⁵ even above the constitution.

¹ Law on Copyright and Related Rights of 1976.

² Ramona Livera (2015). Chapter 73: Laws of Cyprus with Commentary. Introduction to Cyprus law. Neocleus.

³ Synodinou, T. E. (2019). Copyright news from Cyprus. RIDA n°261, July 2019.

⁴ Cyrill P. Rigamonti (2007). The Conceptual Transformation of Moral Rights, 55 Am. J. Comp. L. 67.

⁵ The 2006's constitutional reform added an Article 1A according to which: "*No provision in the Constitution can be deemed as overriding any legislation, acts or measures enacted or taken by the Republic which are obligatory as a member state of the European Union, nor does it hinder Regulations, Directives or other binding provisions or measures of a legislative nature enacted by the European Union from having legal force in the Republic.*"

However, it should be noted that even in the common law countries, Copyright is seen as a “creature of statute”⁶. Characteristically, Law 59/1976 states that “*No copyright or right in the nature of copyright shall subsist otherwise than by virtue of this Law or of some other enactment in that behalf.*”⁷. It means that the difference between common law and continental law is in the context of copyright law more a difference of philosophy and approach than a difference of methodology of law. In other words, in the field of copyright law, Cypriot case law does not have the force of source of law and on the contrary the courts are bound to interpret the existing legislation as it is.

Therefore, Cypriot copyright law can be summarily described as a conjunction between a model incorporation into national law of the EU acquis and a tradition of common law. The result of this union is difficult to assess. The Law of 1976 has been amended multiple times to incorporate the multiple harmonization and adaptation to the digital age efforts of the EU legislator,⁸ but without enough care on the overall cohesion of the text. Consequently, the interpretation of this law presents unnecessary complications and difficulties.

2.2. Practical challenges: the fragile Cypriot copyright ecosystem

Economically, the situation of copyright law in the island is characterized by a paradox: Cyprus features an IP Box regime offering up to 80% tax relief on qualifying Intellectual Property income, taxed effectively at 2.5%, with the purpose to attract tech and creative industries⁹. This nexus-based system aims to enhance Cyprus's role as an IP hub, providing low taxation on royalties and capital gains from IP assets. However, at the same time, the relevant copyright law's ecosystem remains extremely fragile, mainly regarding the role and efficiency of collective management societies (Collective management Organizations - CMOs).

Indeed, relatively few CMOs operate in Cyprus. It should be recalled that CMOs are practically a mandatory element of the functioning of Copyright law, as they ensure that a link exists between

⁶ Microsoft Corp. v. Grey Computer, 910 F. Supp. 1077 (D. Md. 1995).

⁷ Article 19 Law 59/1976.

⁸ Sganga, C. (2024). The past, present and future of EU copyright flexibilities. *International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law*, 55(1), 1–28.

⁹ Income Tax Law of 2002 (Law 118(I)/2002), Section 9(1)(k).

the rightsholders and the users, guaranteeing remuneration to the first and legality to the second. Law 65(I)/2017¹⁰ transposes EU Directive 2014/26/EU, governing CMOs and multi-territorial licensing for online music use. It mandates registration with the Copyright and Neighbouring Rights Authority under the Department of Registrar of Companies and Intellectual Property, which maintains public registries on the question. Amendments in 2024 sparked constitutional review; the Supreme Court ruled certain changes unconstitutional¹¹ for overly restricting CMOs' rights without justification, balancing rightsholder protections under EU Charter Article 17(2).¹²

Then, the Copyright Authority is in the new legislative framework the philosophical stone of the ecosystem. For instance, the Copyright Authority is vested with quasi-jurisdictional powers to determine fair remuneration in certain situations.¹³ Nonetheless, this Authority has not yet been activated and the establishment of the CMO registry is still pending. It should be noted that Copyright law's practical efficiency depends on the existence of CMOs covering core activities: most CMOs specialize in music, covering public performance rights, mechanical reproduction, and neighboring rights for performers and producers, some CMOs concern visual arts (licensing reproduction and public display of images, paintings, and photography), others focus on literary works (managing reprographic rights for books and texts in education or publishing and sometimes also covering theater performances and scripts), and finally, other CMOs specialize in audiovisual (handling film, TV synchronization, and broadcasting rights). It should be noted that most of the CMOs are branches of Greek CMOs.

The main CMOs in Cyprus in the field of music are “PRS for Music (Cyprus branch)”¹⁴, which is a recognized collective management organization handling authors' and publishers' rights (often registered locally as a branch or affiliate of PRS for Music UK), “CNR” (Copyright Neighbouring Rights)¹⁵, Dionysos Zagreas for actors¹⁶, and GRAMMO,¹⁷ which is a society managing rights of

¹⁰ The collective management of copyright and related rights and multi-territorial licensing of rights for online use of musical works Law 65(I)/2017.

¹¹ Supreme Constitutional Court of Cyprus, Report No. 5/2024, 9 April 2025.

¹² Nicoletta Epaminonda, Tatiana Synodinou, Philippe Jougoux. Collective management in Cyprus: a constitutionalist approach, Kluwer Copyright Blog, June 4, 2025.

¹³ For instance, Article 10G of Law 59/1976 states that “ *In the absence of an agreement between a collective management organisation and an operator of retransmission services, or between an operator of retransmission services and a broadcasting organisation, on the granting of a licence for the retransmission of broadcasts, any of the parties concerned may request the Copyright and Related Rights Authority to act as an intermediary*”.

¹⁴ <https://www.prsformusic.com/our-global-network/prs-managed-territories/cyprus>

¹⁵ <http://www.cypriusmusicrights.com/>

¹⁶ <https://www.zagreascy.org/>

¹⁷ <https://grammo.com.cy/en/>

phonogram and videogram producers, active in Cyprus and issuing licences for public performance and other uses. There are also two associated Greek CMOs operating in Cyprus : ERATΩ (Collective management of singers' neighbouring rights) and APOLLON, which represents musicians' neighbouring rights.

Nonetheless, it should be noted that the practical absence of the Authority does not entail a complete paralysis of the system. Existing CMOs continue to work and collect fees for their members. Characteristically, in the relatively recent case PRS v Tsokkos Hotel in 2024,¹⁸ PRS, a copyright collecting society, alleged that the King Evelthon Beach Hotel (owned by Tsokkos Hotels) was broadcasting musical works from its repertoire without permission, both in rooms and public areas, in 2015. The Court recognised that PRS is a legitimate Collective Management Organisation, and rejected the allegations of fraud or lack of legitimacy of the plaintiffs, who won the case. In conclusion, it can be asserted that, if then existing and famous CMOs can continue their work, this instability also works as deterrence to the creation of new CMOs in Cyprus.

2.3. Overview of relevant Teaching and Research General principles of Copyright law

From a human-rights perspective (which, as we will see below, is not at all irrelevant to the discussion of copyright law) teaching and research relate to several fundamental rights: the imperative of access to culture,¹⁹ freedom of the arts,²⁰ the right to education,²¹ and the freedom of expression²². Nonetheless, the idea that human rights should directly interfere with the mechanisms of Copyright law has been ruled out by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) in the landmark cases Pelham (C-476/17)²³, Funke Medien (C-469/17)²⁴ and Spiegel Online (C-516/17)²⁵, in which the Court held that fundamental rights such as freedom of expression,

¹⁸ THE PERFORMING RIGHT SOCIETY LTD (PRS) v. A. TSOKKOS HOTELS PUBLIC LTD — no 523/2016 (2.9.2024).

¹⁹ Article 13 of the EU Charter of fundamental rights.

²⁰ Article 22 of the EU Charter of fundamental rights.

²¹ Article 14 of the EU Charter of fundamental rights.

²² Article 11 of the EU Charter of fundamental rights.

²³ CJEU (2019). Pelham GmbH and Others v. Ralf Hütter and Florian Schneider-Esleben (Case C-476/17), ECLI:EU:C:2019:624.

²⁴ CJEU (2019). Funke Medien NRW GmbH v. Bundesrepublik Deutschland (Case C-469/17), ECLI:EU:C:2019:623.

²⁵ CJEU (2019). Spiegel Online GmbH v. Volker Beck (Case C-516/17), ECLI:EU:C:2019:625.

artistic freedom, and the right to information cannot directly override copyright protection. Instead, any balancing must occur strictly within the framework of the exceptions and limitations exhaustively listed in Article 5 of the InfoSoc Directive²⁶. However, it should not be concluded that human rights' logic, and specifically the concept of proportionality, is absent from copyright law (as analyzed below, see 3.1).

This study will therefore mainly focus on the list of exceptions to the rightsholders' prerogatives, as listed in the Cypriot legislation (see section 3). Additionally, some copyright law's mechanisms will be explored that indirectly affect freedom of teaching and research (see section 4).

However, before exploring all the relevant exceptions to teaching and research, it should be highlighted that the core principles of copyright law are unfortunately to some extent misunderstood, with the consequence that copyright law is in practice seen as more restrictive than it actually is. This point is especially significant in Cyprus, where the development of copyright law has historically been more limited..

Notably, the distinction between idea and expression stands at the heart of international Copyright law. This principle explains that copyright only protects original expressions of creativity, not mere ideas (and by extension data, algorithms or information). It then establishes a dichotomy between works of mind, which are concrete expressions of an idea, and thus can be protected, and mere ideas, that should always remain free of protection.

In the context of research and teaching, an adequate and complete understanding of this principle is a prerequisite for grasping the general equilibrium of the legal framework. This principle is inscribed in the legislation at Section 3, which states that “ *(a) In no case shall the protection recognized under this Law extend to the ideas, procedures, systems, methods (including methods of operation), principles and elements which are expressed in the protected object. (b) If an idea, process, system, method (including methods of operation), principle and element can only be expressed in one and only one way, this unique way (expression) is not recognized as a protection under this Law*”²⁷.

²⁶ Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society. Official Journal of the European Communities, L 167, 10–19.

²⁷ Article 3 (3) (a) and (b) of Law 59(I)/1976.

This principle has also been notably applied by the courts in the landmark case *Sokratous v. Gruppo Editoriale Fabbri*.²⁸ The Cypriot Supreme Court rejected the plaintiff's claim that Umberto Eco's famous book "The name of the Rose" counterfeited the plaintiff's previous work. Although indeed the plaintiff's book also presented the story of a monk in a monastery playing the role of a detective, this similarity was found to be at a conceptual level. In other words, the similarity of ideas was not relevant of copyright law, which only is interested in the protection of a specific expression.

In summary, it should be stressed that teachers, librarians and researchers do not even need to have recourse to the multiple exceptions (see section 3) or special legal mechanisms (section 4) provided by copyright law when they only want to present an idea or an information.

²⁸ *Sokratous v. Gruppo Editoriale Fabbri – Bompiani and "Gnosi" publications*, (1997), 1 AAΔ 1204.

3. Exceptions and limitations to copyright law in favor of research and libraries

In contrast to the famous US system of “fair use”, the European approach on exceptions and limitations to Copyright law is governed by the principle of a closed list of specific cases in which the rightsholder’s prerogatives are partially or fully neutralized. These cases are to be interpreted, however, through the prism of the current human right’s approach (section 3.1). This methodology is particularly important in Cyprus, where the near-absence of case law on exceptions creates significant legal uncertainty in several areas. Then, this study adopts a broad methodology and selected all the exceptions that can directly or not affect freedom of research, of teaching and the library’s activities (sections 3.2).

3.1. Freedom of expression and the methodology of interpretation of copyright law’s exceptions

Exceptions and limitations to copyright law are governed by a fundamental principle of interpretation known as “three step test”. It finds its source in the Berne Convention,²⁹ which is the fundamental international instrument of unification of the general principles of Copyright law. The UK signed this Convention and after its independence Cyprus expressed its decision to continue to apply the Convention³⁰ and later officially ratified the Treaty.³¹ The test is also present in all the other main international and European instruments of governance of copyright law.³²

The three-step test indicates that an exception to copyright law should respect three basic requirements: to refer to certain special cases, not to conflict with a normal exploitation of the work and not to unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the author. As reformulated by contemporary legal scholars,³³ the third part of the test is to be interpreted as a general principle

²⁹ Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, 1886.

³⁰ Declaration of continued application by Cyprus after the accession of the State to independence: February 24, 1964.

³¹ Law N.62/1976 of 18 December 1976 on the Ratification of the Berne Convention.

³² TRIPS Agreement (Art. 13), WIPO Copyright Treaty (Art. 10), WIPO Performances and Phonograms Treaty (Art. 16), EU InfoSoc Directive (Art. 5(5)). Cyprus, as member of the WTO, is considered to have automatically signed the TRIPS agreements.

³³ Hugenholtz, P. Bernit; Okediji, Ruth (March 7, 2012). "Conceiving an International Instrument on Limitations and Exceptions to Copyright". Amsterdam Law School Research Paper. 2012: 37

of proportionality. However, the three steps test is not only an international instrument but also a part of the European *acquis*, which entails a change of nature.³⁴

This test appears in Law 59(I)/1976 three times. First, the test is inserted as a general reference to all exceptions. It is stated that “ *The exceptions referred to in the provisions of subparagraph (2) and to temporary acts of reproduction shall apply only in certain specific cases which do not conflict with the normal exploitation of the work or other subject matter and which do not unduly prejudice the legitimate interests of the rightholder.*”³⁵ The legislator then inserted it a second time during the reform of the e-learning exception, establishing that this exception and the exception in favor of cultural preservation “*apply only in specific cases which do not conflict with the normal exploitation of the work or other protected subject matter and do not unduly prejudice the legitimate interests of the rightholder*”³⁶. There is also a reference to the test when the specific exceptions in favour of persons with impaired vision are explained³⁷.

The CJEU’s approach in *Pelham*³⁸ must be understood in this broader context, although its exact implications remain debated in the academic literature. While some commentators view the judgment as indirectly endorsing a constitutionalist reading of copyright law, whereas the three-step test becomes a tool for balancing authors’ interests with users’ rights³⁹, others argue that the decision does not, in fact, strengthen the equilibrium between copyright and freedom of expression, but rather reinforces the primacy of exclusive rights⁴⁰. What emerges from *Pelham* is therefore not a consensus, but an unresolved tension: exceptions must be applied proportionately so as not to unduly harm the author’s legitimate interests, yet the Court emphasises that such exceptions cannot be interpreted so broadly as to undermine the overall effectiveness of copyright protection. As a result, the degree to which exceptions may operate as a safeguard for freedom of expression remains contested. Nonetheless, it will be accepted here that the exceptions listed below (section 3.2) should be interpreted under the light of the three-

³⁴ Wymeersch Paulien (2023). EU Copyright Exceptions and Limitations and the Three-Step Test: One Step Forward, Two Steps Back, *GRUR International*, Volume 72, Issue 7, July 2023, Pages 631–642, <https://doi.org/10.1093/grurint/ikad019>

³⁵ Article 7 (6) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

³⁶ Article 28 (2) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

³⁷ Article 7Q (3) of the Law 59/1976.

³⁸ CJEU (2019). *Pelham GmbH and Others v. Ralf Hütter and Florian Schneider-Esleben*, *op.cit.*

³⁹ Geiger, C. (2010). The future of copyright in Europe: striking a fair balance between protection and access to information. Intellectual Property Institute.

⁴⁰ Izyumenko E. (2025) “Copyright as a Freedom of (Artistic) Expression Right? The Dangers and Human Rights Law Misconceptions in the AG’s Opinion in *Pelham II*,” *Kluwer Copyright Blog*.

step test, which means that an interpretation fair to both authors and the public has to be established for each of these exceptions.

3.2. Exceptions for the benefit of Teaching and Research

In the Law 59/1976, almost all the exceptions are regrouped into Article 7 (2), which characteristically starts with the expression “*Copyright does not include the right to control [...]*”. Methodologically, it is obviously not the best solution to present the exceptions and limitations, as an exception does not exclude all of “Copyright” but only a specific prerogative (such as the reproduction right).

It should also be noted that the term “exceptions and limitations” covers two very different situations, that are both presents in the Article 7. Some exceptions are absolute, in the sense that the specific described situation completely escape the control of the rightsholder (but the author’s moral right to paternity is always to be respected nonetheless). Other exceptions have more the nature of a system of mandatory license, in the sense that even if the user is exempted from asking permission, it still has to pay one way or another a fair compensation to the rightsholder⁴¹.

The sections below list only those exceptions that are relevant to research and education.

3.2.1. The Fair dealing defense and its use in Research and Education

The fair dealing defense forms part of the identity of the common law copyright tradition, except notably for the USA, which uses the fair use mechanism. This exception traditionally corresponds to the private copy, research and short quotations exceptions of the continental law’s countries and should not be confused with the American fair use, which is much broader.⁴² The main difference lies in the fact that the fair dealing exception does not require merely fair use, but also

⁴¹ Samuelson, P. (2017). Justifications for Copyright Limitations and Exceptions. In R. L. Okediji (Ed.), *Copyright Law in an Age of Limitations and Exceptions* (pp. 12–59). chapter, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

⁴² Gervais, D. (2009). Fair use, fair dealing, fair principles: Efforts to conceptualize exceptions and limitations to copyright. *J. Copyright Soc'y USA*, 57, 499.

a specific purpose that fits one of the four legitimate purposes described in the law: research, individual use, critical review or reference to current events⁴³.

As we will see below, these four purposes, harmonized at the EU level, are also present in the Cypriot copyright legislation as specific exceptions, which creates a certain overlap. In other words, it is a matter of interpretation whether the fair dealing exception has nowadays a specific content which is not specifically addressed below.

Specifically, it is stated that [copyright law does not cover] “ *The performance of any of the acts referred to above in good faith for the purpose of research, individual use, critical review or reference to current events, provided that, if such use is made public, it is accompanied by acknowledgement of the title and authorship of the work, except where the work has incidentally been included in a broadcast;*”⁴⁴.

Therefore, fair dealing requires good faith and encompasses research, private copy, quotation, report of current events. Generally speaking, it is to be accepted that the Cypriot fair dealing exception is broader than its corresponding provision in the UK’s legislation, as it covers every category of works, whereas the UK’s fair dealing exception only refers to literary, dramatic, musical and artistic works⁴⁵.

Interestingly, the notion of good faith as a prerequisite of the legal framework is to be highlighted. It can be accepted that in this context good faith means objective or subjective absence of knowledge of a potential illegality of the source. This approach would be in line with the landmark CJEU case law *Adam*,⁴⁶ in which it was decided that the benefit of a copyright law’s exception was neutralized when the access to the work was deemed to be illegal.

A distinctive feature of the fair dealing mechanism lies in the reference to research, as it is not an exception specifically regulated in other part of the law. No jurisprudence has developed in Cyprus that would interpret and explain this exception. The Cypriot court in this context will give significant importance to the corresponding analysis from UK on this point. In UK, it is noted that the fair dealing defense covers only non-commercial activities⁴⁷. What matters is not the

⁴³ Synodinou T-E, Jougleux Ph. (2010). *La propriété intellectuelle dans l’environnement académique : approche comparative du système légal français et chypriote*. University of Cyprus Publications, p.54.

⁴⁴ Article 7 (1) (a) of Law 59(I)/1976.

⁴⁵ Section 29(2) of the Copyright Act.

⁴⁶ Court of Justice of the European Union. (2014). *ACI Adam BV and Others v Stichting de ThuisKopie and Stichting Onderhandeligen ThuisKopie vergoeding* (Case C-435/12). ECLI:EU:C:2014:254.

⁴⁷ Section 29 CDPA.

commercial or not activity of the institution, but the specific purpose of the researcher. Also, the use must be fair, which entails a proportionality test. Nonetheless, even in the UK, the meaning of the word ‘research’ does not appear to have been judicially considered⁴⁸. It appears certain that the concept of research differs from that of teaching. In other words, the fair dealing exception cannot be used by universities to justify teaching needs⁴⁹.

In conclusion, it appears that hypothetically this exception could be invoked in rare cases where the researcher’s use of the protected work exceeds the limits of private copy and/or quotation (see below) for some reason, but still corresponds to a fair usage.

3.2.2. Quotation

The exception of quotation, already present in the Berne Convention, constitutes a fundamental part of the overall equilibrium of copyright law. In Cyprus law, short quotation is defined at Section 7 as the “*the quotation of extracts for the purpose of criticism or book presentation, provided that they relate to a work or other subject-matter which have already been lawfully made available to the public and that the source, including the name of the author, is indicated, unless it is established that this is impossible, and that such quotation is in accordance with good morals and its length is justified by its purpose*”;⁵⁰ Additionally, it is also stated that “[*is not controlled by copyright law*] (i) *the reading or recitation by a person to the public or in a broadcast of any plausible extract from a published literary work, provided that it is accompanied by sufficient acknowledgment*”;⁵¹.

This exception is to be interpreted on the light of the relevant EU case law. Although it seems *prima facie* as rather limited, its role as main component of the freedom of expression’s influence on copyright law is not to be underestimated. By consequent, the CJEU has opted for a broad definition of this exception. The exception has a broad scope, because it is y not limited to literary works and could apply to every kind of work, such as pictures, video or music.

Characteristically, in the *Funke Medien* (“Military Reports”) case⁵², the Court confirmed the flexible scope of quotation. The excerpt used must be justified by the purpose (context) and not

⁴⁸ British Academy. (2006). Copyright and research in the humanities and social sciences. British Academy.

⁴⁹ *Universities UK Ltd v Copyright Licensing Agency Ltd; Design and Artists Copyright Society Ltd (Intervening)* [2002] RPC 36, pp. 693–727.

⁵⁰ Article 7 (2) (f) of Law 59(I)/1976.

⁵¹ Article 7 (2) (i) of Law 59(I)/1976.

⁵² CJEU (2019). *Funke Medien NRW GmbH v Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (Case C-469/17, ECLI:EU:C:2019:623). Judgment of 29 July 2019.

strictly limited by pre-set length criteria. It means that, contrary to popular belief in higher education, quotations are not limited to 10% of a work. The percentage of authorized use is determined by the purpose, on the basis of the three-step test. In other words, a test of proportionality is applied between the legitimate interest of the researcher and/or the teacher and the scope of the harm to the interests of the rightsholder.

Furthermore, in the case *Pelham* (“Metall auf Metall”)⁵³, the Court stresses that the size of a quotation is acceptable as long as it supports a critical or comparative purpose. At the essence, any kind of quotation is allowed as long as it serves the purpose of facilitating a dialogue between the author and the public. Therefore, in some circumstances whereas the use passes the proportionality test, it is even acceptable that the quotation exception covers the totality of the work.

Consequently, although the Cypriot law refers to “excepts”, the CJEU has confirmed in the case *Spiegel Online*⁵⁴ that quotation may include complete or partial reproduction of a work if justified by the purpose of the quotation and if it does not unproportionally affect the rightholder’s prerogatives. It can be concluded that there is a general gap between the wording of the exception, inspired by the traditional view inherited from the Berne Convention, and the actual legal framework of the exception, whose broad interpretation has triggered a debate in the literature whether it constitutes a kind of European fair use exception⁵⁵ or not⁵⁶.

The practical implications of this exception in the fields of libraries, research and higher education are wide-ranging and diverse. Libraries could curate online exhibitions and include short excerpts from out-of-print novels to contextualize an author’s influence, display low-resolution images of artworks to illustrate a theme, or quote snippets from historical newspapers to show how events were reported at the time. They can also enhance catalogues by adding short quotations from the work itself to help users understand tone or subject matter, including thumbnail images of book covers or artworks (if lawfully available), or embedding brief

⁵³ CJEU (2019). *Pelham GmbH and Others v Hütter & Schneider-Esleben* (Case C-476/17, ECLI:EU:C:2019:624). Judgment of 29 July 2019.

⁵⁴ CJEU (2019). *Spiegel Online GmbH v Volker Beck* (Case C-516/17, ECLI:EU:C:2019:625). Judgment of 29 July 2019.

⁵⁵ Aplin, T., & Bently, L. (2020). *Global mandatory fair use: the nature and scope of the right to quote copyright works* (Vol. 56). Cambridge University Press.

⁵⁶ Parkin, J. (2019). The copyright quotation exception: not fair use by another name. *Oxford University Commonwealth Law Journal*, 19(1), 55-90.

descriptive excerpts from critical reviews. In higher education, lecturers can rely on the quotation exception to enrich teaching materials

3.2.3. Private copy and photocopies

The general exception of private copy, together with its special counterpart for photocopies, constitute, together with quotation, the most fundamental parts of the equilibrium of copyright law. Cypriot copyright law states that [copyright law does not cover] “*reproduction in any medium made by a natural person for private use and for non-direct or indirect commercial purposes, provided that rightholders receive fair compensation that takes into account whether or not the technological measures are applied to the work or other subject-matter in question*”⁵⁷ and specifically “*(p) reproduction on paper or similar media, using any kind of photographic technique or by any other method producing similar results, other than scores, provided that the rightholders receive fair compensation*”⁵⁸;

Therefore, the exception covers any reproduction of a protected work for private use. Although this exception is not limited to a specific purpose such as education or research, it is a very useful exception for researchers and students, notably because it allows them to gather articles, even in digital form, for their studies, or simply take notes in the classroom. As for the quotation exception, this exception does not impose a certain percentage of allowed use.

However, the exception imposes the payment of a fair compensation. In practice, this fair compensation is possible only by using a system of a levy that is computed on the system of photocopy itself or on the sale of any medium of reproduction. However, this legal framework needs two prerequisites: one CMO specialized in collecting this levy and distributing it back to the authors, and a regulation (typically through an executive Order) to fix the exact percentage of levy and to determine what medium (such as photocopiers, hard drives, etc.) are concerned. Therefore, a certain legal uncertainty exists regarding the application of this exception.

Based on the relevant CJEU case law, it is accepted that Member States have discretion to set thresholds (e.g., *de minimis* harm) for when levies apply, provided the rules respect equal

⁵⁷ Article 7 (2) (o) of Law 59/1976.

⁵⁸ Article 7 (2) (p) of Law 59/1976.

treatment⁵⁹. However, it is implied that the system of levy is an intrinsic part of the exception. Without levy, it can be argued that the exception of private copy would not pass the three-step test. Due to the current absence of levy in Cyprus, two interpretations are possible: either private copy is possible as a user's right even without a levy, or private copy is de facto neutralized and impossible for the users to invoke. In the first interpretation, the lack of a statutory levy only triggers state liability. In the opinion of the author, the second interpretation seems to correspond to the CJEU's approach, but litigation (or ultimately intervention by the legislature) would be necessary to solve the issue. In this context, the recent case *Reprobel*⁶⁰ is of the utmost importance, as it establishes that private entities (specifically here a CMO, as it exercises a mission of public service) can be made liable for a defective transposition of the EU *acquis* which does not take into account a correct interpretation of the notion of fair remuneration.

In other words, The *Reprobel* judgment is a landmark ruling because the Court held that when EU law requires fair compensation, Member States must implement a system that actually ensures rightsholders receive that compensation. Conversely, it means Cyprus may currently be in breach of EU law on this point. From the point of view of users, also, a doctrinal uncertainty subsists as courts may treat the exception as inoperative.

3.2.4. Teaching and e-teaching exception

The teaching and e-teaching exceptions have recently received considerable attention from the Cypriot legislature (as the exception was amended in 2022). Teaching exception is regulated at Section 7 while the situation of e-teaching is to be found at Section 29 of the Law 59/1976. The first article states that “ *[is not controlled by copyright law the] use for illustrative purposes only in teaching or scientific research, provided that the source is acknowledged, including the name of the author, unless this is found to be impossible, and where justified by the non-commercial purpose pursued, provided that rightholders receive reasonable compensation and without prejudice to the provisions of Articles 26 and 28 relating to the online use of the works:*

⁵⁹ CJEU (2015). *Copydan Båndkopi v Nokia Danmark A/S* (Case C-463/12, ECLI:EU:C:2015:144). Judgment of 5 March 2015.

⁶⁰ CJEU (2025). *Reprobel CV v Copaco Belgium NV*. (Case C-230/23, ECLI:EU:C:2024:951). Judgment of the Court (First Chamber) of 14 November 2024..

Provided that an excerpt of a work used for the purposes of this paragraph may not exceed five percent (5%) of the total work, excluding works of poetry, unless otherwise provided in a relevant agreement:

It is further understood that the exception and limitation provided for in this paragraph shall not apply to the extent that appropriate licenses are readily available on the market, according to which the acts referred to in this paragraph are permitted and which meet the needs and specificities of educational establishments:

It is further provided that, in the event that the licences referred to in the second reservation are granted, they are notified by the rightholders to the Copyright and Related Rights Authority, which publishes them”⁶¹.

All the fundamental components of the exception as defined at EU level can be found in the Cypriot legislation: the exception is limited to use for illustrative purposes only and for non-commercial purposes., and a mechanism of fair compensation is established. Nonetheless, two significant practical differences exist. First, in the Cypriot legal framework, an incredibly low threshold of 5% of the total work is determined, above which the exception cannot be invoked. On the contrary, the EU exception sets no percentages. Second, the exception imposes fair remuneration on the rightholders while the EU exception does not mandate compensation.

The EU exception for teaching and research purposes is not mandatory. Thus, there is no typical issue of compatibility of Cypriot copyright law with the EU acquis on this point. Nonetheless, it is to be accepted that the Cypriot legislative framework is extremely strict and practically neutralizes the scope of the exception. It would be virtually impossible for educational establishments to maintain the threshold of 5% and the fact that they would in any case have to pay fair compensation means there is no incentive to use the exception rather than negotiate licences.

In parallel, the teaching exception was significantly modernized in 2019 with the Copyright in the Digital Single Market Directive⁶², which created a mandatory digital and cross-border teaching exception. However, the Directive allows Member States significant discretion in its implementation, notably through the so-called licensing carve-out (whereby Member States may

⁶¹ Article 7 (2) (r) of Law 59(I)/1976.

⁶² Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC (Text with EEA relevance.), ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/790/oj> .

exclude certain works if suitable licenses are easily available and visible to educational establishments) and the possibility to set specific conditions, limitations, and thresholds.

Accordingly in Cyprus, Section 26 establishes that “*the digital use of works and other subject matter is permitted for the sole purpose of illustration in teaching, to the extent justified by the non-commercial purpose pursued*”⁶³. However, it accompanies this exception with three cumulative requirements. First, the use must be “*carried out under the responsibility of an educational institution on its premises or other premises or through a secure electronic environment to which only pupils or students and the educational staff of the educational institution have access*”⁶⁴. Practically, it means that the exception may cover use of protected works for pedagogical purposes on a digital platform such as Moodle or Blackboard, when access is restricted to the students. Second and as always, the moral right of paternity must be preserved when possible (that is, mention of the source and name of the author)⁶⁵. Third, a mechanism of fair compensation is instituted⁶⁶.

Importantly, in the same way as for the teaching exception, a threshold of 5% is established⁶⁷. Furthermore, the exception is altogether neutralized in the case where “appropriate licences” are readily available on the market which permit the use of protected works for teaching purpose in a digital environment, and which are described and meet the needs and specificities of educational establishments⁶⁸. For the scope of transparency and foreseeability of the law, this situation is deemed to occur only when such licences are notified to the Copyright Authority and published on their website⁶⁹.

In conclusion, the practical scope of the e-learning exception is extremely narrow. Not only did Cyprus activate the carve-out, the threshold of 5% neutralizes its practical interest, even if the question of the application of the exception persists while the Authority is still pending. However, contrary to the learning exception, the e-learning exception is mandatory in the EU. It is a matter of interpretation, but it can easily be argued that this extremely strict threshold leads to a practical denial of the existence of this exception, in violation of the EU *acquis*.

⁶³ Article 26 (1) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

⁶⁴ Article 26 (1) (a) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

⁶⁵ Article 26 (1) (b) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

⁶⁶ Article 26 (1) (c) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

⁶⁷ Article 26 (2) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

⁶⁸ Article 26 (3) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

⁶⁹ Article 26 (4) of the Law 59(I)/1976.

On the one hand, it should be mentioned that the issue of the potential non-conformity of the 5% ceiling with EU law is not settled law and indeed the EU legislator allows in this case wide margin for national conditions as long as the exception is meaningful.

On the other hand, as a matter of comparison, it should be noted that Germany opted for a threshold of 15% of a published work for teaching, examination, and internal research purposes⁷⁰ and full use is allowed for illustrations (e.g., photos, graphics), individual articles from the same professional or scientific journal, works of minor scope, and out-of-print works may be used in full. Similarly, in Spain, the exception allows use of small fragments or isolated images for illustration of teaching without remuneration, excluding musical scores, single-use works, textbooks, and manuals without threshold and use of a chapter, article, or up to 10% of a work for universities and public research centers, with mandatory remuneration⁷¹. However, most of the Member States (France⁷², Belgium⁷³, Italy⁷⁴ for instance) have not instituted any threshold, although also most of the Member States refer to the use of “excerpt” of the work. In sum, the legal framework can be characterized as fragmented and, partially, inadequate.⁷⁵ In this perspective, the extremely low threshold of the Cypriot implementation is only a symptom of a general issue of optimizing the exception at the EU level.

3.2.5. Text and Data mining

Added to the EU acquis in 2019, the so-called “text and data mining” exception has gained much attention following the subsequent generative AI revolution. It would unfortunately exceed the scope of this study to detail the ongoing debate between scholars that argue this exception entirely covers the genAI’s activities and those that consider from a teleological perspective that the exception cannot realistically apply to this new reality. Nonetheless, as a quick reference to the ongoing debate, it should be mentioned that, for instance, Martin Senftleben argues that copyright exceptions permitting TDM for AI training can be compatible with the international three-step test and, in principle, provide a lawful basis for AI training—especially where an

⁷⁰ § 60a UrhG.

⁷¹ Articles 32.3 and 32.4 of LPI.

⁷² Article L. 122-5-4 CPI.

⁷³ Art. 75 CDE.

⁷⁴ Article 70 of the Legge sul Diritto d’Autore (LDA).

⁷⁵ Priora, G., Jütte, B.J. & Mezei, P. (2002). Copyright and Digital Teaching Exceptions in the EU: Legislative Developments and Implementation Models of Art. 5 CDSM Directive. IIC 53, 543–566.

opt-out mechanism is respected.⁷⁶ On the contrary, Eleonora Rosati contends that TDM is not necessarily synonymous with AI training and cautions against assuming unlicensed training is covered by the TDM exceptions⁷⁷.

Cyprus copyright law strictly follows the letter of the EU legislation. It defines "text and data mining" as an automated analytical technique that aims to analyze data in digital form, with the aim of producing information, including patterns, trends and correlations.⁷⁸ Then it distinguishes between two situations: data mining for scientific research and data mining in general (including for commercial purposes). Concretely, Section 24 of the Cypriot law inserts the mandatory exception of data mining for scientific purposes to the right of reproduction, but only in favor of research organisations and cultural heritage institutions and relating to protected works that are available in legal access⁷⁹.

The general exception is identical to the previous one, with one major difference: the exception only applies provided that the use of works has not been expressly restricted by the rightholders in an appropriate manner, such as by machine-readable means in the case of content that has been made publicly available online. This exception has been introduced in verbatim in Cypriot law⁸⁰.

A specific attention should be given to its famous opt-out mechanism, that works as guarantee of the rightholders' interests. AI can train only on freely accessible content whereas the author has not expressly indicated their refusal to be referenced. It is worth noting that the Creative Commons organization has revised its open licences policy accordingly. It did not create a new licence, but instead developed a "CC signals"⁸¹ policy which is a framework of human- and machine-readable signals to express dataset reuse preferences for AI. In other words, it provides a standardized option for the rightholders to use or not the opt out mechanism.

⁷⁶ Senftleben, M. (2025). GenAI and the copyright three-step test – Do TDM exceptions for AI training conflict with a work's normal exploitation? GRUR International, Volume 75, Issue 1, January 2026, Pages 1–2, <https://doi.org/10.1093/grurint/ikaf113>

⁷⁷ Rosati, E. (2024). Is text and data mining synonymous with AI training? Journal of Intellectual Property Law & Practice, 19(12), 851–852. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jiplp/jpae092>

⁷⁸ Article 2 of the Law 59/1976.

⁷⁹ Article 24 (1) of the Law 59/1976.

⁸⁰ Article 25 (3) of the Law 59/1976.

⁸¹ See Creative Commons. (2025, June 25). Introducing CC Signals: A new social contract for the age of AI. Creative Commons. <https://creativecommons.org/2025/06/25/introducing-cc-signals-a-new-social-contract-for-the-age-of-ai/>

Before concluding on the TDM exception, it should be noted that the AI Act⁸², expected to enter fully into force in 2026, introduces transparency obligations for providers of general-purpose AI models, including the requirement to document whether copyrighted materials have been used for training and to respect opt-out signals expressed in machine-readable form. Although the AI Act does not amend copyright law, its Article 53 operates in functional parallel with the opt-out mechanism of Article 4 of the DSM Directive, reinforcing the expectation that AI developers verify lawful access and honour rightsholder exclusions.

3.2.6. Parody

Although its use is somehow relative in the education sector and is (normally) even less relevant in the research sector, the exception of parody plays a tremendous role as a key element of the protection of freedom of expression in copyright law, in general, and merits to be noted. This exception did not previously exist in Cypriot law; it was introduced with the transposition of the DSM Directive and now applies to both analogue and digital uses. The exception is inserted in Section 7, which allows for free use of a protected work “*for caricature, parody or pastiche*”⁸³.

The notions of caricature, parody or imitation are not defined. Nonetheless, the CJEU has applied a broad definition of these notions in the landmark Deckmynn case⁸⁴. It entails from the decision that the exception both covers the situation where the user intends to parody the work and to parody through the work.

The humorous intent remains an incredible subjective matter and the court preferred to focus on other criteria, such as the existence of noticeable differences between the original and the parody. In parallel, no originality of the parody is requested, although some obvious differences are needed for the parody’s user to be in position to understand it is not the original work but a parody. In conclusion, the silylline mention of parody in the corpus of the exceptions in Cypriot law could greatly benefit from the clarification brought by the CJEU in this field.

⁸² Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act), ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>

⁸³ Article 7 (2) (k) of Law 59/1976.

⁸⁴ Court of Justice of the European Union. (2014, September 3). Johan Deckmynn and Vrijheidsfonds VZW v. Helena Vandersteen and Others (Case C-201/13, ECLI:EU:C:2014:2132).

3.2.7. The library exception and the preservation exception

Libraries, educational organizations and museum enjoy the benefit of a broad exception in Cypriot copyright law, closely mirroring the corresponding exception instituted by InfoSoc Directive⁸⁵. It is stated that [are not covered by copyright law] “ *specific acts of reproduction of a work carried out by publicly accessible libraries, educational establishments or museums or by archives and which are not intended, directly or indirectly, for economic or commercial gain, subject to the exceptions and limitations provided for in Articles 24 to 44*”⁸⁶.

At first glance, this exception seems broad. The EU legislator, however, mentions in the Recitals of the Directive that “*this should be limited to certain special cases covered by the reproduction right*” and that “*Such an exception or limitation should not cover uses made in the context of on-line delivery of protected works or other subject-matter*”⁸⁷.

At the same time, The CJEU has opted for a broad interpretation of the exceptions protecting the libraries, reasoning that the objective of promoting culture would be undermined if libraries were not also permitted to digitise and reproduce their printed collections for purposes covered by the existing exceptions⁸⁸. Nonetheless, it should be noted that this decision refers to Article 5(3)(n) of Directive 2001/29/EC, which pertains to the right of libraries to digitize books they hold for research or private study and to propose them on dedicated on-site terminals. However, this exception had not been incorporated in Cypriot law.

The situation is more complex than it initially appears, as the legal framework governing libraries extends beyond this point. In the definitions given in the Law 59/1976, libraries belong to the broader notion of “*cultural heritage institution*”⁸⁹. Therefore, this exception is to be read nowadays in conjunction with the more recent exception in favour of the preservation of cultural heritage introduced by the DSM Directive⁹⁰ and inscribed at Section 27 of the law. It is explained that “*cultural heritage institutions are permitted to make copies of a work or other subject matter of protection which is permanently in their collections, in any form and by any means, for the*

⁸⁵ Directive 2001/29/EC, Article 5(2)(c).

⁸⁶ Article 7 (2) (j) of Law 59/1976.

⁸⁷ Recital 40 of the InfoSoc Directive.

⁸⁸ CJEU, C-117/13 Technische Universität Darmstadt v. Eugene Ulmer [2014] EU:C:2014:2196.

⁸⁹ According to Article 2 Law 59/1976, “*cultural heritage institution or organisation' means a library, museum or gallery, archive or institution of cinematographic or audio heritage accessible to the public;*”

⁹⁰ Directive 2019/790 on Copyright in the Digital Single Market.

*purpose of preserving such works or other objects of protection and to the extent necessary for such preservation*⁹¹.

Interestingly, it is added that “*acts of reproduction carried out by cultural heritage institutions or organisations for purposes other than the preservation of works and other subject-matter in their permanent collections shall be subject to the authorisation of the rightholders, unless such acts may be carried out under other exceptions or limitations provided for in European Union law*”⁹².

In conclusion, although the classic library exception allows for any act of reproduction that has a non-commercial nature, the preservation clause intervenes and precises the scope of what an act of non-commercial reproduction may be. Two interpretations are possible. It could be argued that the specific preservation exception does not fully replace the broader library exception. However, it could also be accepted that, since the insertion of the new Section 27, this exception only covers acts of reproduction for preservation purposes (digitally or not), with the very unfortunate consequence to excessively narrowing the libraries’ privileges. Indeed, Section 7 does mention that it applies “*subject to the exceptions and limitations provided for in Articles 24 to 44*”, while the preservation exception lies at Section 27.

The right interpretation depends on the specificities of the State Member’s legislation. In countries whereas the classic library’s exception was formulated in a way to depend on a medium, was linked to remuneration, or could be overridden by contract, the new preservation exception provides a much-needed freedom to libraries⁹³. However, in Cyprus, which was one of the very few Members States that chose to transpose the classic library’s exception into their national legal framework⁹⁴, and where the classic exception was already formulated in very broad terms, the new exception could have the potential, in contrary, to affect its scope, at least for libraries. At the opposite, for museums and other cultural heritage institutions, the preservation exception is the only means to protect their activity.

⁹¹ Article 27 (1) of Law 59/1976.

⁹² Article 27 (1) of Law 59/1976.

⁹³ E. Rosati (2021) Copyright in the Digital Single Market: Article-by-Article Commentary. OUP, Ch. on Article 6.

⁹⁴ The exception can only be found in Portugal, Malta, Ireland, Hungary, Czech Republic, Italy, Finland, Denmark and Cyprus. See : Sganga, C (2024). The Past, Present and Future of EU Copyright Flexibilities. IIC 55, 5–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40319-023-01413-9>.

3.2.8. Public lending and e-lending

In law 59/1976, lending is defined as " *the making available for use, for a limited period of time, and not for direct or indirect economic or commercial benefit, when made by institutions that are open to the public.*"⁹⁵. In the EU, lending is established as an exclusive right for copyright holders⁹⁶. Therefore, no lending activity should occur without the permission of the rightsholder. This situation would obviously create an impossible burden to public libraries, so most member states implemented this EU legislation as a remuneration right rather than maintaining it as a purely exclusive right. It means public lending is excluded from the prerogatives of the rightsholder, on the condition they receive compensation. This notion is strictly controlled by the CJEU on the light of the three-step test, with the consequence that the European court does not only request for a system of compensation to be instituted, but also emphasizes the concept that a mechanism of fair compensation should be introduced, that correspond to the extent of the damages on the commercial exploitation of the work because of the lending⁹⁷.

In Cyprus, however, the situation is dealt with through Section 7 (7), which states that : " (i) *The Authority may, at the request of any public institution, by decision derogate from the rule of the exclusive right of authors to consent or prohibit public lending of originals and copies of works protected by copyright or other protected subject matter thereof, subject to the payment of remuneration to the authors for such lending.*

(ii) The Authority may determine the remuneration referred to in subparagraph (i) taking into account the objectives of cultural promotion.

*(b) The Minister may, by decree, exempt certain categories of institutions from the payment of the remuneration provided for in paragraph (a) where the lending carried out by the institutions in question is a secondary occasional activity"*⁹⁸.

Therefore, in Cyprus, there is no direct exception in favour of public lending. On the contrary, the situation is let to the discretion of the Authority, which, however, does not function in practice as explained above. In other words, the Cypriot law has clearly not incorporated the public lending exemption provided for in Article 6 of the Rental and Lending Rights Directive⁹⁹. Practically, it

⁹⁵ Article 2 (1) of Law 59/1976.

⁹⁶ Article 7 (1) (a) Law 59/1976.

⁹⁷ CJEU, 10 Nov 2016, C-174/15 (Vereniging Openbare Bibliotheken), ECLI:EU:C:2016:856.

⁹⁸ Article 7 (7) (1) of Law 59/1976.

⁹⁹ Directive 2006/115/EC.

means that the situation is theoretically entirely dealt with through private ordering (licencing by the CMO). Nowadays, there has not been a payment yet from libraries under this public lending mechanism¹⁰⁰.

Another issue of debate is the transposition into Cypriot law of the court's findings in the landmark VOB case¹⁰¹. The CJEU recognized that libraries could lend e-books under the same legal regime as physical books, provided certain conditions are met. Specifically, the Court adopts the "one copy – one user" model, which means that e-lending falls under the public lending exception only if the library has acquired the e-book lawfully, and the e-book is lent to one user at a time, for a limited period, and the copy becomes unusable for others during the loan.

This important development has not been translated into the legislative corpus in Cyprus. Certainly, lending is defined as "*making available for use, for a limited period of time, and not for direct or indirect economic or commercial benefit, when it is made by institutions that are open to the public*";¹⁰² which means that the broad definition does not strictly exclude e-books from the mechanism. However, due to the very sensitive nature of the interpretation, a legislative clarification would be welcomed. The need for a mandatory legislative mechanism becomes particularly evident in light of the fact that existing agreements between libraries and publishers currently exclude any possibility of e-lending.

3.2.9. Exception in favor of visually impaired persons

Cyprus has signed and ratified the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.¹⁰³ This Convention holds as a matter of principle that "*States Parties shall take all appropriate steps, in accordance with international law, to ensure that laws protecting intellectual property rights do not constitute an unreasonable or discriminatory barrier to access by persons with disabilities to cultural materials*"¹⁰⁴. Additionally, the Marrakesh Treaty of 2013 organized by the WIPO has marked a milestone in the situation of access to culture for persons with disabilities. This

¹⁰⁰ World Intellectual Property Organization Standing Committee on Copyright and Related Rights (2024). SCCR/45/7 Annex: reports of countries operating an active PLR system. Council Report, Cyprus, p.43. https://www.wipo.int/edocs/mdocs/copyright/en/sccr_45/sccr_45_7_annex.pdf

¹⁰¹ Ibid 97.

¹⁰² Article 2 of Law 59/1976.

¹⁰³ Law 8(III)/2011 - The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and Related Matters (Ratification) Law of 2011.

¹⁰⁴ Article 30 (3) of the Convention.

international instrument has been, first, incorporated to the EU acquis through two Directives¹⁰⁵, and then, to the Cypriot legislation.

First, the list of exceptions contains a general exception in favor of persons with disabilities that concerns any act on protected work that would not have a commercial nature, and which is justified by the handicap¹⁰⁶.

Then, as explained above, a specific legal framework directly inspired by the Marrakech Treaty, is added to this exception, which covers the specific situation of persons with impaired vision. First, the law adds some specific definitions for this legal framework¹⁰⁷ : 'accessible format copy',¹⁰⁸ "beneficiary", which covers situations of blindness, person with amblyopia or with an incapacity to read or hold a book, 'authorised entity' which means an entity authorised or recognised by decree of the Minister or the corresponding competent authorities in other Member States to provide beneficiaries with education, training, adapted reading or access to information, on a non-profit basis, and may also be a public body or a non-profit organisation providing the same services to beneficiaries as one of its main activities; as an institutional obligation or in the context of public interest missions, and also the notion of 'Work or other subject matter', which means a work in the form of a book, a specialised review, a newspaper, a magazine or other type of publication, notation, including sheet music, and related illustrations, on any medium as well as in audio form, such as phonographed books, and in digital format, which is protected by copyright or related rights and is published or made available to the public by another lawful means.

Then, the following exceptions are inserted : the beneficiary, or a person acting on his behalf, may produce a copy in an accessible format of a work or other subject matter to which the rightholder has legal access and which is for the exclusive use of the beneficiary¹⁰⁹ and an authorised entity may make a copy in an accessible format of a work or other subject matter to which it has lawful

¹⁰⁵ Directive (EU) 2017/1564 and Regulation (EU) 2017/1563.

¹⁰⁶ Article 7 (2) (s) of law 59/1976 states that "[is allowed] any use of a work, which is made for the benefit of persons with disabilities, which is directly related to the disability and is not of a commercial nature, to the extent required by reason of the disability in question, without prejudice to the provisions of Articles 7O to 7IC";

¹⁰⁷ Article 7P of the Law 59/1976.

¹⁰⁸ Which means a copy of a work or other subject matter that gives the rightholder access to the work or subject matter, in an alternative way or in an alternative form, including by enabling that person to have effective and comfortable access as a person without any disability or disability as referred to in the definition of 'rightholder';

¹⁰⁹ Article 7Q (1) of the Law 59/1976.

access, or to present, make available, distribute or lend a copy in an accessible format to a rightholder or other authorised entity on a non-profit basis for the exclusive use by the rightholder¹¹⁰.

The legal framework places significant emphasis on the role of the “authorised entity”, which is entrusted with carrying out the acts permitted under the exception for the benefit of persons with print disabilities¹¹¹. In Cyprus, however, there is no publicly accessible and centralised list of authorised entities formally recognised by the authorities. This lack of transparency creates uncertainty for both beneficiaries and institutions wishing to operate under the exception. A structured dialogue between the Government and relevant stakeholders would, therefore, be desirable in order to establish clear procedures for designation and oversight, and potentially to create or formally endorse a dedicated body responsible for coordinating these functions. The main issue is that the concept of authorized entity needs approval through executive order and it could be more efficient to accept that certain categories of cultural institutions such as libraries should be by default seen as authorized entity.

3.2.10. Report on current events

The Cypriot law also covers as exception the report of current events. It is stated that is allowed the “*reproduction in the press, communication to the public as defined in subsection (1) above or making available published articles on economic, political or religious current affairs or broadcast works or other subject-matter of the same type, where such use is not expressly prohibited and provided that the source, including the name of the author, is indicated, or use of works or other subject-matter in the presentation of current affairs; to the extent justified by the informational purpose and provided that the source, including the name of the author, is acknowledged, unless this is found to be impossible*”¹¹².

This exception is in line with the Berne Convention,¹¹³ as it transposes Article 10bis almost verbatim, but expands the permitted acts to include communication to the public and making available right. This exception is also present with identical terms in the EU acquis¹¹⁴.

¹¹⁰ Article 7Q (2) of the Law 59/1976.

¹¹¹ Article 7R of the Law 59/1976.

¹¹² Article 7 (2) (g) of the Law 59/1976.

¹¹³ Article 10 bis of the Convention.

¹¹⁴ Article 5 (3) (c) of the Infosoc Directive.

4. Other specific mechanisms relevant to research and culture

Research and education do not only benefit from the specific exceptions analyzed above, but some specific legal mechanisms are instituted that promote access to culture. Specifically, first the national policy relevant to open access will be studied (4.1). Then, the EU law's inspired mechanism of out of commerce works will be described (4.2). This analysis will lead to the (non) existence of a secondary publication right in Cyprus (4.3). Libraries only benefit from the very specific mechanism of orphan works, which, as we will see, does not work in Cyprus (4.4). Finally, some general remarks on the general principles of copyright law regarding fair remuneration (4.5) and the communication to the public's right (4.6) will complete this analysis.

4.1. Open access – Cypriot national policy

Open Access (OA) has become a genuinely transformative force in research and education because it removes the financial, legal, and technical barriers that often restrict access to knowledge. In a scholarly environment where learning increasingly depends on quick and fair access to reliable scientific information, OA ensures that students, teachers, and researchers can benefit from the most recent research findings. This approach is consistent with wider European and international efforts that promote the free circulation of scientific knowledge as a source of innovation, transparency, and social progress. The European Commission has supported OA for many years as the preferred way to disseminate publicly funded research, emphasizing its societal value and its contribution to the European Research Area¹¹⁵.

At the same time, OA functions entirely within the boundaries of copyright law. Copyright remains the legal framework that determines how creative and academic works may be shared, reused, adapted, or transformed. OA does not remove copyright; instead, it relies on rightsholders granting broader permissions through licensing systems, most commonly Creative Commons licenses. These agreements clarify how works may be accessed, distributed, reused, or developed further. They aim to preserve creators' rights while supporting the public interest in

¹¹⁵ European Commission. (2012). Commission Recommendation of 17 July 2012 on access to and preservation of scientific information (2012/417/EU). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32012H0417>

wide knowledge dissemination. This equilibrium echoes current legal and policy developments in Europe, including the EU’s 2019 Directive on open data and on the reuse of public sector information, which encourages openness while continuing to protect material covered by copyright,¹¹⁶ and which was transposed in Cyprus in 2021¹¹⁷.

Cyprus formally adopted a National Policy for Open Access to Scientific Information in 2016, approved by the Council of Ministers¹¹⁸. In May 2022, Cyprus updated this policy and broadened it into a full National Policy for Open Science Practices. This new framework covers Open Access to scientific publications, FAIR/Open research data, use of Open Science infrastructures and services, and the adoption of broader Open Science practices. The new objective was clearly more ambitious, as the 2022’s plan was to establish open access as the norm for 2026. The policy establishes Open Science as the default framework for publicly funded research in Cyprus.

It should also be mentioned that the issue of open access recently gained a lot of attention at EU level, with the emerging “Fifth Freedom”: the free movement of knowledge¹¹⁹. This principle has become central to current debates on strengthening open access in Europe. Recent work around the ERA Act (which could be adopted as EU Regulation as early as end of 2026) underscores that completing the European Research Area requires removing barriers to the circulation of scientific knowledge and establishing a harmonised, equitable open-science ecosystem¹²⁰. The European Parliament’s ITRE Committee¹²¹ has similarly stressed that realising this Fifth Freedom demands structural reforms such as a Union-wide secondary publication right and a mandatory scientific research exception, both of which directly reinforce open-access objectives by enabling unrestricted, cross-border reuse of publicly funded research.

¹¹⁶ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast), ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj>

¹¹⁷ The Open Data, Re-use of Public Sector Documents and Information and Related Matters Law of 2021 (Law 143(I)/2021).

¹¹⁸ The National Policy of the Republic of Cyprus for Open Access to Scientific Information was approved by the Council of Ministers on 25 February 2016 (Decision No.: 80.309) accessible at : [National Policy of the Republic of Cyprus for Open Access to Scientific Information](#)

¹¹⁹ European Economic and Social Committee (EESC), “The ERA Act: unlocking the fifth freedom” (Press summary, 16 July 2025).

¹²⁰ See for instance the remarks of the European University Association (EUA), “EUA’s recommendations to increase the European Research Area’s impact and achieve the fifth freedom”, <https://eua.eu/news/eua-news/euas-recommendations-to-increase-the-european-research-areas-impact-and-achieve-the-fifth-freedom.html> (last accessed 02/2026).

¹²¹ Justus Dreyling, ITRE: Free circulation of scientific knowledge is key to ERA Act, (February 25, 2026), <https://communia-association.org/2026/02/25/itre-free-circulation-of-scientific-knowledge-is-key-to-era-act/> (last accessed 02/2026).

In conclusion, the legal framework relevant to OA in Cyprus is fully compliant with the existing EU's directives and international standards, but the field is actually in a state of radical changes. It remains to be seen whether in practice this translates to a broader use of OA by Cypriot researchers. According to the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative (COKI), adoption of OA is in net progression, at 50%¹²².

4.2. Non exploitation, out of commerce works and the right of revocation

Copyright law is based on the principle that authors must have the economic benefit of their creation, allowing them to continue their work, which indirectly guarantees the users a broader access to culture. However, in practice, producers or publishers may fail to play their role of intermediaries in this process. For example, it could be that the commercial exploitation of a protected work is not economically enough attractive, to the detriment of both the authors and the users. As the work hasn't yet fallen into public domain, its diffusion thus enters a dead-end. This problematic is known in copyright law as "out of commerce" works and to remedy the potential harm to access to culture, the EU legislator has found some ways to bypass the inaction of the rightsholder.

In Cyprus, first, a specific exception is established that deals with the situation, that predates the European intervention in this field. It is stated that is allowed "*the broadcasting of a published work in which no collective management organisation or independent management entity is interested, provided that, subject to the provisions of this Article, the holder of the broadcasting right in the work receives reasonable compensation, to be determined, in the absence of an agreement, by the Copyright and Related Rights Authority*"¹²³. It should be noted that here it is explicitly explained that the application of the exception is conditioned to the payment of a fair compensation to the rightsholder, defined by the Copyright Authority.

Therefore, Cyprus creates a statutory licence for broadcasting a published work when no CMO or independent management entity is "interested" in the work. Then, the broadcaster pays reasonable compensation, which is set by the Copyright Authority if no agreement is reached.

¹²² See : <https://open.coki.ac/country/CYP/> (last accessed 02.2026).

¹²³ Article 7 (2) (l) of the Law 59/1976.

This exception is somehow unusual, as it is not inspired by a similar regulation at EU or international level. Its application is certainly problematic, as it remains uncertain what does the reference to “interested CMO” means, what is the agreement referred to in the text, and whether the mechanism works a priori or a posteriori of the broadcasting. The procedure is not described, but it is assumed that the broadcasting organization will in practice broadcast the work without authorization because of the lack of existing CMO, and then the rightholder will request to the Copyright Authority to define a fair compensation. Nonetheless, in absence of an active Authority that would state on the compensation, the exception remains in lethargy.

In parallel, a specific legal framework, inspired by EU law, is created that focuses on “out of commerce” works at Section 29, entitled “Use of works and other subject matter not commercially available by cultural heritage institutions or organisations” and at Section 41, which refers to the so-called “Right of revocation”.

The notion of out of commerce works is defined by the legislator, who considers that *“A work or other subject matter is considered to be out of commerce where it can be presumed in good faith that the entire work or other subject matter is not available to the public through normal commercial channels, after a reasonable effort has been made to determine whether it is available to the public”*¹²⁴.

Section 29 allows for a CMO to sign non-exclusive licensing agreement for non-commercial purposes with a cultural heritage foundation for the purpose of reproducing, distributing, communicating to the public or making available to the public non-commercially available works which are permanently in the collection of the institution¹²⁵. This licensing agreement must obey to the principle of fair licensing¹²⁶. The interesting part here is that the CMO may do so even without authorisation from the rightsholders of the specific work, from the moment it is sufficiently representative of the concerned field in general¹²⁷. For instance, a renowned CMO specialized in representing musicians may authorize a public library to organize a cultural event where rare recordings of a concert that cannot be found on the market are played. It has to be a CMO that represents Cypriot rightsholders¹²⁸, as this legal framework does not apply in case a

¹²⁴ Article 29 (5) of the Law 59/1976.

¹²⁵ Article 29 (1) of the Law 59/1976.

¹²⁶ Article 29 (1) (b) of the Law 59/1976.

¹²⁷ Article 29 (1) (a) of the Law 59/1976.

¹²⁸ Article 29 (6) of the Law 59/1976.

collection is composed principally by works originating from third countries¹²⁹, unless the CMO itself is also from this country¹³⁰.

In case no CMO fulfils the conditions to be in position to provide such a license¹³¹, the legal framework also provides for an exception¹³². Cultural heritage institutions or organisations may then freely make available for non-commercial purposes works or other subject matter which are permanently in their collections, provided that they mention the name of the author and that *“such works or other subject matter are made available on non-commercial websites”*¹³³.

The dual application of this exception at Section 29 and of the exception of Section 7 mentioned above is not without creating a certain dose of uncertainty in Cyprus. The two exceptions certainly overlap in their scope: while the first one introduces a statutory license for broadcasting where no CMO is interested in exploiting the work, the second one is activated where no CMO is fit to grant mandatory license. Nonetheless, their differences must be highlighted: the first one gives a general right to broadcast a work, but a fair compensation must be paid, while the second one only covers non-commercial exploitations of the work by cultural institutions. In this case, no fair compensation is requested, but strict conditions apply (and more importantly, the impossibility to proceed to licencing with a CMO).

Furthermore, it is worth noting that both mechanisms of mandatory licencing and the exceptions in Section 29 are dispositive law (rules of dispositive law are those rules of law whose application may be excluded by contrary private will such as contracts). The law allows for the rightholders to even exclude their works from the mechanism after its activation as the CMO must comply with its written statement within a reasonable time¹³⁴.

Finally, the situation of out of commerce works entails some derogations to the general principles of contract law, once again dictated by the EU legislator. By exception, it is possible for the author to withdraw from their contractual engagement with the publisher, by revoking in whole or in part the licence or the transfer of their rights or just by revoking the exclusive nature of the

¹²⁹ Article 29 (7) of the Law 59/1976.

¹³⁰ Article 29 (8) of the Law 59/1976. It should be noted that this paragraph refers to the first paragraph of the Article, not to the seventh, but as it does not make sense, it should be accepted, through the reference to “in that third country” that it actually refers to paragraph 7.

¹³¹ Article 29 (3) of the Law 59/1976.

¹³² Article 29 (2) of the Law 59/1976.

¹³³ Article 29 (2) (b) of the Law 59/1976.

¹³⁴ Article 29 (4) of the Law 59/1976.

agreement¹³⁵. This right of revocation, however, is allowed only on the strict condition that no exploitation of the work has taken place at any time, which means, obviously, that a reasonable amount of time must be given to the other party from the date of conclusion of the agreement for the granting of authorisation or the transfer of rights¹³⁶.

Finally, it is worth noting that a very specific provision exists in the Copyright law in favour of the performer of a musical work. In case, at least 50 years after the publication of the phonogram, the producer ceases to offer for sale copies of the phonogram in sufficient quantity or to make it available to the public, the performer may terminate the contract¹³⁷.

In conclusion, a relatively new element of equilibrium has been incorporated into EU law. Directly inspired by a similar legal mechanism in USA, this right of revocation avoids the limits and critics of heavy formalism expressed on its cousin¹³⁸. Nonetheless, this right only applies when the work has not been exploited at all, which gives it a scope much narrower than the scope of the mechanism regulating out-of-commerce works.

4.3. (the lack of) Secondary publication right in Cyprus

A secondary publication right (SPR) in EU copyright literature is a legal mechanism that allows authors of publicly funded research to make their work openly available even after signing a publishing contract. Several Member States only (Germany, France, Austria, Belgium, the Netherlands, Bulgaria, Slovenia) have adopted SPR provisions, each with distinct scope, conditions, and legal effects¹³⁹. In other words, such a legal mechanism does not yet exist in Cyprus.

A comparative approach of this mechanism shows a common definition and divergences on the condition of application. First, as definition, it is commonly agreed that the mechanism touches on the thorny issue of free access to funded research. The general philosophy of this mechanism

¹³⁵ Article 43 (1) of the Law 59/1976.

¹³⁶ Article 43 (3) of the Law 59/1976.

¹³⁷ Article 12 (8a)(i) of the Law 59/1976.

¹³⁸ Authors Alliance. (2021). Reversion of copyright in Europe: Rights reversion and the new right of revocation under Directive 2019/790. In *Spotlight on rights reversion & termination of transfer*. Authors Alliance.

¹³⁹ Sganga, C., Margoni, T., Senftleben, M., & Szkalej, K. (2025). Towards a European Research Freedom Act: A proposal for an EU-wide secondary publication right. *IIC – International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law*, 56, 1516–1552. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40319-025-01620-6>

is to consider that funded scientific research should be accessible to the public, as it has been paid by the public itself and its dissemination corresponds to a general interest. However, the national approaches greatly differ in the application of this philosophy. One of the main points of dissension lays in the creation or not of a retention period, called “embargo”. For instance, when a period of 12 months of embargo is instituted, the mechanism of free access is possible only after this lapse of time has passed. The embargo is here to ensure that commercial exploitation, together with a remuneration of the author, is possible, at least for a period of time. It should be noted that data shows overwhelming support for SPRs among researchers, librarians, and institutions¹⁴⁰.

The European Research Area (ERA) Act is designed to be the first EU-level legislative instrument explicitly focused on research governance, aiming to realize what EU institutions call the “fifth freedom”: the free movement of knowledge. The Commission already announced plans to adopt this Act in 2026. Nonetheless, the results of the public consultations have not been yet published and it is early to distinguish whether the proposal will adopt an ambitious mechanism of SPR without embargo or if it will stick to more timid approach on the model of the French and German legislations.

It should be added that the field of scientific publications is nowadays in a dead end, which should greatly concern the Cypriot authority, as the country has transformed in a high education hub. The culture of “publish or perish” leads the researchers to seek high impact journals and the need for international recognition pushes the universities to a greater dependency on non-open tools of research measurement, such as Scopus. At the same time, it is widely recognized that open access significantly enhances the dissemination and impact of knowledge, with studies showing substantially higher visibility and citation rates compared to subscription-based publications¹⁴¹. Copyright reform and the introduction of a broad secondary publication right appear to be beneficial to society in this context in order to break this dominating culture against open access. It is worth noting that doing so at the EU level allows for harmonisation and so easier

¹⁴⁰ Wyber, S. (2026, January 26). Looking for a home for the secondary publication right: Lessons from national legal frameworks. Kluwer Copyright Blog. <https://legalblogs.wolterskluwer.com/copyright-blog/looking-for-a-home-for-the-secondary-publication-right-lessons-from-national-legal-frameworks>

¹⁴¹ Zhu, Q., Li, J., Chen, Y., Zhang, Y., Li, J., & Ming, J. (2025). Exploring the citation and impact advantages of open access papers in hybrid journals: A case study of biochemistry publications. *Publications*, 13(4), 64. <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications13040064>.

cooperation, while coordination in these very specific fields is always beneficial for smaller countries like Cyprus.

4.4. Orphan works and libraries

The issue of the mass digitalization of libraries content became a huge legal challenge some years ago, foreshadowing the subsequent AI revolution. The thorny issue specifically concerned the so-called “orphan works”, which are protected works for which it is for some reason practically impossible to find the rightholder and ask them for authorization. The EU then created a specific legal framework to deal with this¹⁴², which has been transposed in Cyprus in Section 7K, almost verbatim. To summarize the mechanism, libraries and other cultural institutions are bound to proceed to a bona fide diligent search of the rightholder¹⁴³.

If this search is not fruitful, the cultural institution may legally digitize the work,¹⁴⁴ “solely to achieve objectives related to their public interest missions and in particular the conservation, restoration or provision of political or educational access to the works or phonograms included in their collection”¹⁴⁵. It should however send to the “competent authority” record of its search¹⁴⁶. It is worth noting that the competent authority here is not the Copyright authority, but it means the Registrar of Companies¹⁴⁷. Obviously, this multiplication of supervisory authority is far from adequate. The registrar is bound to send the list of orphan works to another institution, at the EU level. The law refers to the Office for Harmonisation in the Internal Market¹⁴⁸, which however does not exist anymore, as it has then been transformed to the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO).

A search on the online database of the EUIPO of orphan works shows that this specific mechanism has never been used in Cyprus¹⁴⁹. There are multiple explanations for this. First, the administrative burden of recording and sending the searches may have discouraged librarians

¹⁴² Seucan, A. (2017). Several aspects regarding orphan works after the adoption of EU Directive 2012/28/EU of the European Parliament and the Council of 25 October 2012. OAJI Journal, 1–10.

¹⁴³ Article 7K (1) of Law 59/1976.

¹⁴⁴ Article 7N (1) of Law 59/1976.

¹⁴⁵ Article 7N (3) of Law 59/1976.

¹⁴⁶ Article 7K (6) of Law 59/1976.

¹⁴⁷ Article 2 of Law 59/1976.

¹⁴⁸ Article 7K (7) of Law 59/1976.

¹⁴⁹ See : [Orphan Works DB](#) (last access 02/2026).

and museum curators. Second, it should be recalled, as explained above, that libraries benefit nevertheless from another exception (see section 3.2.7) which provides them with a lot of freedom in this field. Third, it is also possible that relevant institutions have not become sufficiently aware of this peculiar legal mechanism.

Finally, it is also fair to indicate that Cyprus, as a small country, does not encounter the same difficulties regarding orphan works, that other EU member states. Indeed, the relatively smaller pool of authors and the corresponding smaller dataset entails, in the author's opinion, a greater access and knowledge to their identity or facilitates their identification and maybe this could explain this phenomenon.

4.5. Cypriot contract law, fair remuneration and transfer of rights

Authors' remuneration constitutes a thorny topic in EU Copyright law, as national traditions diverge on this point. While continental countries have generally opted for a principle of speciality, which means that only specific prerogatives of the author, with material and sometimes even temporal constraints, common law countries traditionally accept, on the contrary, the principle of assignment of rights in Copyright law. It means that the author is allowed to transfer not only a specific right, but all rights over the work. Practically, this divergence has tremendous consequences on the mode of remuneration of the author. In the context of the principle of speciality, the author may in principle be remunerated on the basis of the exploitation of the work (principle of proportionality), while if the right is assigned, remuneration takes the form of a lump sum.

A study for the European Commission in 2016 on the Remuneration of Authors of Books and Scientific Journals¹⁵⁰ concluded that the contractual mechanism with the strongest positive effect on authors' remuneration is the legal obligation to specify precisely the scope of the transfer, including geographical scope, duration and modes of exploitation. There is a clear trend

¹⁵⁰ Europe Economics, Guibault, L., & Salamanca, O. (2016). Remuneration of authors of books and scientific journals, translators, journalists and visual artists for the use of their works. Publications Office of the European Union.

in scholarship in EU copyright law¹⁵¹ to call for mechanisms preventing overbroad rights assignments, seen as intrinsically unfair for the author¹⁵².

Cyprus has both kept intact its traditional philosophy and incorporated the new EU acquis on this question. First, it is stated that “*the right of intellectual property shall be transferable either by assignment, or by an order of last will, or by law, as movable property*”¹⁵³. Assignment is therefore generally accepted, with the formal requirement of a written contract¹⁵⁴. A very specific provision concerns the performer of a phonogram. Even in case of assignment, they are entitled to an annual supplementary remuneration, for each full year immediately following the 50th year after the phonogram was lawfully published¹⁵⁵.

In parallel, the EU legislator has pushed in 2019 towards the adoption of a fair mechanism of remuneration of the author. Therefore, in Cyprus law, a new Section 39, entitled “Principle of appropriate and proportionate remuneration”, states that “*In the event that authors and performers license or transfer their exclusive rights for the exploitation of their works or other subject matter, they are entitled to receive appropriate and proportionate remuneration.*”¹⁵⁶. It is explained that the remuneration shall be appropriate and proportionate to the “actual or potential” economic value of the rights licensed or transferred, taking into account the author's or performer's contribution to the overall work or other subject matter and all other circumstances of the case, including market practices or actual exploitation of the work¹⁵⁷.

Therefore, the reference to potential economic value means that the mechanism of assignment is not per se discarded. In other words, it is still possible to assign rights in Cypriot copyright law, on the condition that the remuneration has taken into consideration the potential economic value of the work. However, this creates a degree of uncertainty on the validity of the assignment contract, specifically when the success of the exploitation has not been foreseen by the parties.

¹⁵¹ See for instance, the Opinion of the European Copyright Society. Dusollier, S., Kretschmer, M., Margoni, T., Mezei, P., Quintais, J. P., & Rognstad, O.-A. (2025). Copyright and generative AI: Opinion of the European Copyright Society. European Copyright Society. https://europeancopyrightsociety.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/ecs_opinion_genai_january2025.pdf

¹⁵² Geiger, C., Scalzini, S., & Bossi, L. (2025). Time to (Finally) Reinstall the Author in EU Copyright Law: From contractual protection to remuneration rights. *International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law*, 56, 1866–1913. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40319-025-01647-9>.

¹⁵³ Article 12 (1) of the Law 59/1976.

¹⁵⁴ Article 12 (5) of the Law 59/1976.

¹⁵⁵ Article 12 (8B) of the Law 59/1976.

¹⁵⁶ Article 39 (1) of the Law 59/1976.

¹⁵⁷ Article 39 (2) of the Law 59/1976.

In an era where any content may become “viral” at any time for any reason, the certainty of the payment of a lump sum seems less effective than a proportional remuneration.

From the context of open access, this provision also poses another issue. What is the situation where the author decides to use a Creative Commons (CC) license (a license that typically allows the user to freely use the content without monetary compensation)? It could be argued that the EU efforts to harmonize fair remuneration rights may unintentionally affect creator-controlled licensing models, such as CC licenses, which typically rely on voluntariness and freedom to waive remuneration¹⁵⁸. Nonetheless, a teleological approach of the mechanism should lead to the conclusion that this mechanism of protection of the author does not establish a general and indiscriminate principle of mandatory remuneration which would block free transfer of rights. Indeed, in Section 39, reference is made to licenses of exclusive rights only, which should, by principle, exclude from the mechanism all contractual tools of non-exclusive licensing such as the CC licenses.

Furthermore, a mechanism of contract adjustment is set out in the law at Section 41, that provides for an enforcement of the principle of fair remuneration set at Section 39. Where “*the remuneration initially agreed proves to be disproportionately low in relation to all subsequent relevant revenues derived from the exploitation of the works or performances*”, the authors are entitled to claim additional, appropriate and fair remuneration¹⁵⁹.

Concretely, assignment of rights in Cypriot contract law is still legal but must envisage a fair remuneration, taking into account the economic potential of the exploitation of the work. In case of error of appreciation or deliberate miscalculations, the author may now turn to the courts to enforce their right to fair remuneration, using Section 41 as legal basis.

4.6. Communication to the public

The CJEU has developed an extremely rich case law on the definition of the economic right of “communication to the public”, which is, with the right of reproduction, one of the most fundamental parts of the economical prerogatives of the rightsholder. This right is interpreted broadly and any person who facilitates the transmission of a protected work without

¹⁵⁸ Towse, R. (2018). Copyright reversion in the creative industries: Economics and fair remuneration. *Columbia Journal of Law & the Arts*, 41(3). <https://doi.org/10.7916/jla.v41i3.2023>

¹⁵⁹ Article 41 (1) of the Law 49/1976.

authorization is deemed to infringe copyright law¹⁶⁰. The CJEU specifically struggled to provide an adequate adaptation of the communication to the public's right to the digital age¹⁶¹.

The detailed analysis of this right and the corresponding case law would exceed the scope of this study, but it should be noted that some elements of this case law have directly influenced the Cypriot legislator. Specifically, the legislator mentioned in the definition of the right of communication to the public that *"It is understood that this definition does not include the placement on a website of a hyperlink to works freely available on another website"*¹⁶². This refers to the landmark decisions Svensson¹⁶³ and GS Media¹⁶⁴, which used and adapted the two basic components of the right to communication to the public (the existence of a material action facilitating access and the consequence that a new public is touched by the communication). The Court accepted the idea that a hyperlink which leads to a protected content is indeed an act which facilitates access to the content, but, at the same time, on the condition that this content is freely accessible on the Internet, no new public is concerned by this communication.

Therefore, a hyperlink by itself does not infringe copyright law. By exception, there will be a new public in two cases: the content was not freely accessible (for instance, it was behind a paywall, and the user circumvents the protection) or the content was illegally uploaded. In the last case, however, the situation is very delicate: to require an average user to have knowledge of the legal or illegal status of a protected work on the Internet in order to know if the hyperlink is legal or not would create a disproportionate burden, incompatible with the principles of freedom of expression. Therefore, this case law differentiates the average user (in this case the hyperlink from illegal content is illegal itself only in case where the illegality was obvious) from the professional (a person with an economic interest in creating the hyperlink), who is bound by a duty of care and should make some reasonable efforts to identify the potential illegality of the origin of the work.

This case law has tremendous consequences for teachers and librarians. In the era of cloud computing, the distinction between reproduction and communication is blurred and

¹⁶⁰ CJEU (2010). *Organismos Sillogikis Diacheirisis Dimiourgon Theatrikon kai Optikoakoustikon Ergon v Divani Akropolis Hotel and Tourism AE* (Case C-136/09), ECLI:EU:C:2010:151.

¹⁶¹ For instance see CJEU (2021). *VG Bild-Kunst v Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz* (C-392/19), ECLI:EU:C:2021:181.

¹⁶² Article 2 of the Law 59/1976.

¹⁶³ CJEU (2014). *Svensson and Others v Retriever Sverige AB* (C-466/12), ECLI:EU:C:2014:76.

¹⁶⁴ CJEU (2016). *GS Media BV v Sanoma and Others* (C-160/15), ECLI:EU:C:2016:644.

transmission of cultural or scientific knowledge often passes through communication to the public. It can be a link to an article in a database, an online video shown in class, etc.

The landmark case Renckhoff¹⁶⁵ constitutes, however, a serious warning to teachers, researchers and students alike. In this case, a professor uploaded on the school's portal the essay of one of her students, which had incorporated as illustration a protected photography, that she had found freely accessible online. The photographer found the essay and sued for infringement. The Court considered that in this case there is a reproduction of the photograph on a new medium (the essay) and the situation is not to be assimilated to a mere hyperlink. Therefore, uploading a photo previously published online with authorization does constitute a new communication to the public and the school infringed the photograph's rights.

Although the legal reasoning is flawless, the Renckhoff case is characteristic of the current maze of scientific publications' legal framework. The student's essay incorporated a protected photography. This could have been covered by the private copy exception but not by the teaching exception because of the 5% threshold. It is a matter of interpretation whether the quotation exception would apply (even if the quotation could cover the use of all the work, the use was illustrative only and not for the purpose of dialogue). But the professor uploaded it on the school's portal. The new online teaching exception would not apply for instance in Cyprus, which imposes a threshold of 5% and, nevertheless, the portal's access was not restricted, as requested by the exception. Furthermore, the specific legal framework regarding hyperlinks does not apply as there is an act of reproduction. However, this situation may also be seen as problematic: the action was carried out without commercial purpose, the inclusion was incidental, for the interest of science, and did not harm the commercial or moral interests of the author.

4.7. The legislative framework on Technical Measures of Protection (TPM)

In the text of the Cypriot Law on Copyright and Related Rights (59/1976) there is an explicit definition of technological measures where it is stated that TPM “*means any technology, mechanism or component which, in its normal mode of operation, is intended to prevent or*

¹⁶⁵ CJEU (2018). Land Nordrhein-Westfalen v Dirk Renckhoff (C-161/17), ECLI:EU:C:2018:634.

*restrict acts in relation to protected objects (..)*¹⁶⁶. This definition aligns with Article 6 of Directive 2001/29/EC (InfoSoc), which formed the basis for the incorporation of TPMs into the national laws of the Member States. Article 14B is the central provision of Cypriot law for protection against the neutralization of technological measures. The structure of the article closely follows Article 6 of Directive 2001/29/EC (InfoSoc), which is the basic EU text for TPMs. Basically, it transposes into national law the anti-circumvention obligations of Article 6 InfoSoc.

However, the practical application of this provision may be problematic. Indeed, some exceptions in favour of education and research have been updated in the last EU intervention in 2019 (through the DSM Directive) in such a way that contractual override is now impossible¹⁶⁷. This leads to an illogical situation whereas exceptions such as the data mining are elevated to the rank of right, but the rightful user is still incapable of passing through potential TPMs.

By consequence, Cyprus, as well as many other Member States,¹⁶⁸ has weak or unclear mechanisms on the interrelation between TPMS and users' rights, creating a gap between the formal right and the practical ability to exercise it. Actually, the legislator explicitly mentions that even if the user belongs to a group of users who normally benefit from copyright exceptions (like private copying, education, research, etc.), they are still prohibited from bypassing technological protection measures (TPMs) if they use tools or methods that go beyond what the law allows¹⁶⁹. A general revision of the old TPM's legal framework to ensure that imperative exceptions prevail would then be advised.

Nonetheless, it should also be noted that actually the Cypriot provision contains an error in the transposition of the EU acquis, which, ironically, provides here a great help. Indeed, the provision states that : is illegal "*Anyone who, knowingly or with reasonable grounds to know that they are pursuing this purpose and without the permission of the rightholder, manufactures, imports, distributes, sells, leases, advertises for sale or lease or possesses for commercial purposes, appliances, products or components*"¹⁷⁰ that circumvent TPM. No mention is made of the individual act of circumventing TPM itself, as the use and possession of such a tool for non-commercial purposes is not covered by the law.

¹⁶⁶ Article 2 Law 59/1976.

¹⁶⁷ Article 7 of the DSM Directive.

¹⁶⁸ Marcella Favale, 'Technological Protection Measures and Copyright Exceptions in EU27: Towards the Harmonization' (2011) 33 European Intellectual Property Review 563.

¹⁶⁹ Article 14B (4) of Law 59/1976.

¹⁷⁰ Article 14B (1) of Law 59/1976.

5. Policy Proposals

Three distinct categories of policy proposals appear from this study : a proposal for a general reform (5.1), or, alternatively, a list of targeted legislative reforms (5.2), which should then be accompanied by non-legislative reforms and initiatives (5.3).

5.1. General Legislative Reform

Following the explanations and discussions stated above, it should be accepted that the repeated overlay of EU directives onto the original 1976 statute has generated redundancies, overlaps (notably between the fair dealing exception and subsequent specific exceptions), and interpretive difficulties that are unnecessary and harmful to legal certainty. One possible overarching solution would be to rebuild Cypriot copyright legislation from the ground up, effectively adopting a tabula rasa approach. This means to enact a comprehensive re-codification of Law 59/1976 to replace the current patchwork of successive amendments with a coherent, consolidated text. A new legislation, codifying in a clear and concise way all the EU acquis would provide an attractive for the rightholders and the investors framework, while guaranteeing to all the actors, specifically in the sectors of education and research, more legal certainty.

5.2. Targeted legislative reforms towards a modernization of copyright law in the education and research sectors

Nonetheless, since such a reform can be seen as radical, it is alternatively proposed to amend the existing legislation, correcting the specific issues raised above. Therefore, the following legislative and institutional modifications are proposed to modernise Cypriot copyright law and bring it into conformity with EU law and the needs of a contemporary research and educational environment.

5.2.1. Modification of the name of the Office for harmonization in the Internal Market

- Update the reference in Article 7K(7) of Law 59/1976 from the defunct “Office for Harmonisation in the Internal Market” to the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO), which now operates the orphan works database. This is a straightforward technical correction required to ensure the orphan works mechanism is legally operable.

5.2.2. Reform of the Teaching and E-Teaching Exceptions

- Raise the 5% quantitative threshold in Article 7(2)(r) (teaching exception) and Article 26(2) (e-teaching exception) significantly or abolish it altogether. The current threshold is strikingly low by comparative standards: Germany allows 15% and most EU Member States (France, Belgium, Italy) impose no percentage cap at all. The threshold, combined with the mandatory fair compensation requirement and the licensing carve-out, renders the exceptions practically inoperative. In the case of the mandatory e-teaching exception under Directive 2019/790, the current implementation arguably constitutes a de facto denial of the right conferred, raising questions of compatibility with EU law. A threshold of 10% will be then proposed.
- Review the mandatory fair compensation requirement attached to the teaching exception (Article 7(2)(r)) to assess whether it creates a disproportionate burden on educational establishments, having regard to the three-step test and the need to ensure the exception retains meaningful practical effect. Consider whether compensation should be tied to actual harm rather than applied as an unconditional obligation.
- Clarify the relationship between the licensing carve-out in Article 26(3) and the obligations of the Copyright Authority under Article 26(4) to publish notified licences, so that educational establishments can readily identify whether the licensing carve-out is triggered with respect to specific categories of works. In the absence of a functioning Authority, specify an alternative mechanism for transparency.

5.2.3. Public Lending and E-Lending

- Transpose properly the public lending exemption provided for in Article 6 of Directive 2006/115/EC (Rental and Lending Rights Directive) into Cypriot law. The current mechanism in Article 7(7), which makes public lending entirely dependent on a discretionary decision by the Copyright Authority, does not fulfil Cyprus's EU obligations. A legislative amendment should establish a direct statutory exception for public lending subject to the payment of equitable remuneration, with the Authority's role limited to determining the level of remuneration in the absence of agreement.
- Introduce an explicit legislative provision clarifying that e-lending falls within the scope of the public lending exception, in line with the CJEU's ruling in Case C-174/15 (VOB). The provision should adopt the "one copy–one user" model, conditioned on the library's lawful acquisition of the e-book and the technical neutralisation of the copy during the loan period.

5.2.4. Library and Preservation Exceptions

- Clarify by legislative amendment the relationship between the general library exception in Article 7(2)(j) and the preservation exception in Article 27, to confirm that the general exception retains its independent scope for acts of reproduction that are not for preservation purposes (e.g., on-site access via dedicated terminals). This clarification is especially important given that Cyprus is among the very few Member States that transposed the general library exception, and interpretive uncertainty risks inadvertently narrowing the privileges of publicly accessible libraries. In addition, the dedicated on-site terminal exception should also be incorporated into Cypriot law.
- Propose, at EU level, to introduce a new and clear provision allowing libraries and other cultural heritage institutions to get rid of Technical Protection Measures or to have access to a TPM-free version of the work, while they act in line with their prerogatives, by amending the provisions of Article 14B (4).

5.2.5. Secondary Publication Right

- Introduce a secondary publication right in Cypriot law, allowing researchers whose work has been funded wholly or partially with public funds to make their final accepted manuscripts openly available after a reasonable embargo period, notwithstanding any contractual assignment of rights to a publisher. Cyprus is currently among the minority of EU Member States that has not enacted such a mechanism. Given Cyprus's ambition to become a higher education hub and its 2022 National Policy for Open Science, an SPR would directly support the goal of universal open access by 2026 and bring the country into alignment with Germany, France, Belgium, and the Netherlands. Legislative action at the national level is also advisable in anticipation of forthcoming EU-level developments under the European Research Area Act expected in 2026.
- Adopt a modern vision of secondary publication right. Specifically, the following provisions are proposed for insertion into Law 59/1976: a new Article 39A establishing the right as inalienable and non-waivable; a transitional clause confirming retroactive application to pre-existing contracts for future acts; an emergency override permitting immediate deposit upon cessation, transfer, or insolvency of the publishing entity; and the necessary executive regulations designating national repository infrastructure.
- The provision must precisely describe the eligible works. The right shall apply to journal articles and conference papers resulting from research funded, wholly or in part, by public funds — including national research grants, institutional core funding, and EU Framework Programme contributions. No majority funding threshold is required; any public funding component suffices. Monographs may be incorporated in a subsequent legislative phase. However, the right covers the author accepted manuscript — the peer-reviewed, author-corrected text prior to the publisher's typesetting and layout — thereby preserving the publisher's exclusive commercial value in the version of record. Optionally, the right could also cover doctoral thesis, to follow the recent initiative of the Council of Universities to create a unified national database of thesis.
- Finally, no embargo mechanism will be included in the legislation by default. By exception, for social sciences and humanities, a maximum of three months from first publication may be instituted, reflecting longer commercial exploitation cycles. This ceiling is non-negotiable: contrary contractual extensions are void.

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- Early national legislative action is advisable in anticipation of the forthcoming European Research Area Act, expected to introduce an EU-level SPR in 2026, so as to establish the institutional framework before a potentially less tailored supranational instrument enters into force.

5.2.6. Authors' Remuneration and Contract Law

- Issue guidance or adopt a legislative clarification confirming that the principle of appropriate and proportionate remuneration in Article 39 of Law 59/1976 does not operate as a mandatory obstacle to voluntary non-exclusive licensing instruments, such as Creative Commons licences. Such clarification would remove legal uncertainty for researchers, institutions, and open access infrastructure providers, and would confirm that Section 39 applies only in the context of exclusive licences and assignments.
- Optionally, introduce a principle of proportional remuneration, which corresponds to a more modern approach of copyright law than assignment, unless the specificities of the market sector or technical impossibility imposes the recourse to assignment of rights.

5.3. Non-legislative reforms to be conducted for a modernization of Cypriot copyright law

The administration may also influence the effectiveness of the legal framework by adopting some targeted measures through Executive Orders or campaigns of awareness and guidelines.

5.3.1. Activation of the Copyright and Related Rights Authority

- Make the Copyright and Related Rights Authority fully operational without further delay. The Authority's inaction currently paralyses several key mechanisms of the copyright system: it prevents the determination of fair remuneration for public lending (Article 7(7)), blocks the statutory broadcasting licence for out-of-commerce works (Article 7(2)(l)), neutralises the private copy levy system, and prevents the publication of market licensing information required for the licensing carve-out under the e-teaching exception (Article 26(4)).

5.3.2. Completion of the CMO registry

- Complete the establishment of the CMO registry under the Department of the Registrar of Companies and Intellectual Property, as required by Law 65(I)/2017, taking due account of the constitutional constraints identified by the Supreme Constitutional Court in its ruling of 9 April 2025.

5.3.3. Private Copy Levy System

- Adopt the necessary executive Order to activate the private copy and reprographic levy system provided for in Articles 7(2)(o) and 7(2)(p). This regulation should specify: (i) the categories of media and devices subject to the levy; (ii) the applicable levy rates; and (iii) the CMO or other body responsible for collection and distribution to rightsholders. Absent this regulation, the private copy exception risks being either de facto inoperative or incompatible with the three-step test, as no fair compensation reaches rightsholders.

5.3.4. Quotation Exception and Legal Awareness

- Disseminate guidance to educational institutions, libraries, and researchers clarifying the actual legal scope of the quotation exception in Article 7(2)(f), as interpreted by the CJEU in *Funke Medien*, *Pelham*, and *Spiegel Online*. Contrary to widespread practice, quotations are not limited to an arbitrary percentage of a work; their permissible extent is determined by proportionality and purpose. This misconception results in systematically over-restrictive self-censorship in higher education and research.
- Issue guidance to teachers, students, and researchers on the legal implications of the *Renckhoff* ruling (Case C-161/17) regarding the upload of protected works to educational platforms and the interaction of the communication-to-the-public right with the e-teaching exception. In particular, clarify that uploading a photograph found freely online to a school portal without restricted access constitutes an infringement not covered by the teaching exception in its current form, and that the exception requires a secure electronic environment accessible only to enrolled students and staff.

5.3.5. Orphan Works

- Reduce the administrative burden attached to the orphan works mechanism in Article 7K by streamlining the diligent search requirements and simplifying the recording and notification procedure. The current mechanism has never been used in Cyprus, partly due to its procedural complexity. Consider designating a single competent authority (ideally the Copyright Authority rather than the Registrar of Companies) as the contact point for orphan works notifications, and align the legislative text with the EUIPO database which now serves as the EU-level repository.
- Launch targeted awareness-raising initiatives directed at libraries, museums, archives, and other cultural heritage institutions regarding the scope and conditions of the orphan works mechanism, the quotation exception, and the out-of-commerce works regime. Misunderstanding of the existing legal framework leads practitioners to apply more restrictive standards than the law actually requires.

5.3.6. Accessibility for Persons with Visual Impairments

- Issue the executive order required under the Marrakesh Treaty framework (Articles 7O–7R of Law 59/1976) to formally designate “authorised entities” empowered to produce and share accessible format copies for persons with print disabilities. Consider providing that public libraries and publicly accessible cultural heritage institutions are by default recognised as authorised entities, without requiring individual ministerial approval, so as to maximise the practical benefit of the exception for beneficiaries.

6. Conclusion and recommendations

Generally speaking, and this also is verified on the specific context of OA, the situation of the Cypriot copyright law may be described as relatively, and unnecessarily, complex and ineffective. The haphazard juxtaposition of the EU *acquis* on copyright law with the preexisting legislation has led to repetitions and overlaps (see the fair dealing exception), while the gap between the legislation and its actual enforcement, compounded by the lack of administrative supervision, entails serious difficulties in applying the legal framework. It is in both the interest of the authors and of the cultural and scientific organizations to have an efficient, clear, and adaptable legal framework that would regulate access to knowledge.

Therefore, a thorough revision of the legal framework in the form of a *tabula rasa* is advisable at national level. But experience shows that in the field of copyright law this revision could also draw inspiration from the EU legislator itself. Various projects have already discussed the simplification and harmonization of EU Copyright law through the instrument of codification. The most advanced project was, for instance, the Wittem Group's European Copyright Code¹⁷¹.

Such an initiative (either a national re-codification or an European initiative) would provide grounds for reopening the negotiations on the current equilibriums of copyright law, with more emphasis on the protection of education and research. As noted above, the teaching exception as currently applied in Cyprus raises serious questions of compatibility with the EU law, due to its very low threshold (5%). Furthermore, no secondary publication right and a nearly inexistant mechanism of public lending right exists in Cyprus. And as discussed also, the question of the author's remuneration has become more and more complex due to the conflict between two incompatible philosophies of author's remuneration.

In conclusion, it is to be accepted that the EU had made multiple interventions already in the field of Cypriot Copyright law. It appears, however, clearly that it is in the best economic and cultural interest of Cyprus to request even further intervention, as multiple flaws in the practical functioning are nowadays presents in the legal framework.

¹⁷¹ Hugenholtz, P. B. (2014). The Wittem Group's European Copyright Code. In I. Stamatoudi & P. Torremans (Eds.) *EU Copyright Law: A Commentary*. Edward Elgar Publishing. Institute for Information Law (IViR). https://www.ivir.nl/publicaties/download/ILS_29_chapter17.pdf